

Mass Media Contribution in Resilience Capacity Building Before, During and After Disaster in The Niger Delta Region, Nigeria

Oboatare A. Ikutegbe ✉

Centre for Disaster Risk Management and Development Studies, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Jones Gilbert I. Ayuwo ✉

Department of Linguistics & Communication Studies, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Sunday A. Amama ✉

United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Abuja, Nigeria

Andrew. A. Obafemi ✉

Department of Geography & Environmental Management, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper examines the contribution of mass media in resilience capacity building before, during, and after disasters in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. It explores the concept of mass media, objectives and impacts of risk communication, the cost of oil spills, and capacity building required to achieve community resilience to Oil spills-related disasters in the study area. Quantitative data collection methods were used to elicit information from respondents selected for the study, while descriptive and inferential statistics like the ANOVA and Multiple Regression analysis were employed for data presentation and analysis. Findings revealed that only 32.7% of the sampled respondents agreed that mass media adequately informs them about the available resources and support system for affected communities and that it effectively communicates environmental risk and hazards associated with oil spills with 38.8% agreed, while 84.6% agreed that media informs better after a disaster had occurred, 62.5% during, and just 26.7% before it occurs. It stressed the need for media communicators to acquire increased capacity in terms of risk knowledge (84%) and existing local adaptation and coping measures 68.1%. It recommends improved knowledge capacity by the media to enable them to inform the community at risk promptly and correctly, invest in and utilize modern ICT platforms for their reportage, improved response in line with global best practice of media role in disaster management, while government should organize workshops to create more awareness on mass media usage towards enhanced community participation for resilience capacity building of oil spilled communities in the Niger Delta.

Keywords: *resilience, disaster, mass media, risk communication, environmental pollution.*

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Introduction

Effective communication across all phases of a disaster—before, during, and after—is a vital

component of comprehensive disaster management. According to Chaturvedi and Shah (2023), media and communication channels play a crucial role in disaster scenarios by distributing

critical information, educating the public, identifying high-risk zones, issuing timely alerts, and covering unfolding events. These media efforts support emergency response operations by conveying real-time updates from affected regions, promoting public safety, guiding officials and decision-makers, and coordinating efforts among volunteers and humanitarian agencies (Chaturvedi & Shah, 2023).

Media performs several essential functions, including educating the public, disseminating information, and supporting disaster preparedness and response (Yulian, 2023). As Liu et al. (2020) highlight, typical communication tools used during disasters - such as radios, telephones, television broadcasts, newspapers, and social media - are essential for relaying updates and instructions to both victims and the broader public. Yuliana (2023) further underscores the necessity of timely and effective communication not only during emergencies but also throughout the recovery phase. In essence, the media's responsibility during disasters is to inform, educate, and communicate efficiently with all stakeholders to enhance community resilience and build trust.

Environmental degradation resulting from oil exploration activities by multinational corporations in Nigeria's Niger Delta has had severe consequences on local biodiversity (Ugochukwu & Ertel, 2008). The pollution of air, water, and soil has worsened ecological deterioration, leading to food insecurity. This is largely attributed to the destruction of aquatic ecosystems, crop failure, and the degradation of arable land, all of which undermine local livelihoods (Nkanang et al., 2017). Oil spills, a specific focus of this paper, have contributed significantly to the destruction of mangrove ecosystems and water bodies, further impacting biodiversity and causing widespread socio-economic and environmental harm to host communities over the years (Nkanang et al., 2017).

These environmental disasters have also disrupted traditional rural livelihoods such as fishing, boat building, and agriculture. The rising frequency of oil spills has been linked to declines in fish and crop productivity, thereby reducing

income and threatening food security in rural communities of the Niger Delta. According to Höppner et al. (2012), this has entrenched economic disparity, leaving many communities unable to benefit from their natural resources. While the extent of damage caused by oil spills varies depending on the size of the spill and geographical factors, the socio-economic and environmental impacts can be profound. Consequently, oil spills have remained one of the most pressing environmental threats in the Niger Delta for several decades (Nkanang et al., 2017; Ugochukwu & Ertel, 2008). Common causes include pipeline sabotage, neglected maintenance, equipment failure, and outdated infrastructure—some pipelines are reportedly over 40 years old and in urgent need of replacement.

On a global scale, the media is recognized as a powerful force for change and development across multiple domains (Akinfeeye, 2010; Dwivedi & Pandey, 2013). It plays multiple roles—informing, educating, persuading, mobilizing, interpreting events, and providing entertainment. Media reports help individuals adapt to societal changes and stay informed about developments in their communities. Recognizing the critical role of the media in disaster risk reduction, global leaders established action frameworks in Japan (2005) and Sendai (2015) that position the media as a central actor in raising awareness, for instance, about the health risks associated with oil spills and how to mitigate them (Adekunle et al., 2016). Research increasingly supports the idea that media can contribute to the resilience of oil-impacted communities (Ukhurebor et al., 2021).

Although effective communication and media engagement have been emphasized as essential tools for enhancing disaster resilience globally (Höppner et al., 2012), there has been relatively little focus on building the communicative and social capacity of media practitioners themselves. Despite the significant harm caused by oil exploration in the Niger Delta, the dissemination of information and communication regarding the risks remains insufficient. In response to these challenges, this paper explores how the media can contribute to strengthening community resilience through

efficient risk communication before, during, and after disaster events. It also seeks to address existing gaps by analyzing the role of mass media, the goals and impacts of disaster risk communication, the economic and environmental costs of oil spills in the Niger Delta, and the capacity-building measures necessary to enhance community readiness for disaster situations linked to oil spills.

Conceptual Clarification and Review

Concept of The Mass Media

A piece of media is something that is intended to be seen by a wide number of people. With the introduction of newspapers and periodicals, the phrase was first utilized to mark the beginning of mass communication and the dissemination of information to the general public (Popper, 2021). The media has taken on a significant role in modern society thus the purpose of the media is to enlighten and educate the public. (Kapoor, 2015). The importance of addressing environmental issues is recognized by the media, which often serves as a platform for raising awareness and advocating for sustainable practices and policies. An intriguing and impactful avenue for addressing this issue lies in the use of media. In the contemporary information era, data travels instantly across various platforms such as television, radio, print, and digital outlets. Beyond simply spreading information, the media holds significant sway in guiding public perception and can strongly impact policy and individual decision-making (Fastercapital, 2024). As Sarma et al. (2021) note, in today's digitally connected world, media outlets play a vital role in shaping how people perceive global events and influencing the choices they make in response. Besides, the media also reflects public interest, creating a cyclical relationship where the media's coverage of environmental issues is influenced by and influences public concern and awareness. Additionally, media professionals say they sense what the audience is interested in, highlighting the symbiotic relationship between media content and audience preferences (Saikia, 2017).

Functions of the Mass Media

- **Supplying vocational information:** A greater segment of the community can access professional and vocational information thanks to the media.
- **Supplying a range of information:** These media assist in providing the general public with a variety of information. People pick up new information rapidly.
- **Promoting societal awareness and responsibility:** Through the media, people can learn about many societal issues and their part in addressing them. People are clear on their obligations to the country and their rights.
- **Educational programmes:** With the aid of the media, people can develop good habits for a variety of programmes and make productive use of their downtime. It also affects people's behavior through a variety of programmes.
- **Function as an informal agency:** Modern culture no longer views the media as a variety of informal education. Due to their extensive and organized covering of educational topics, these organizations are known as non-formal.

Objectives of Risk Communication in Disaster Management

Communicating risk effectively plays a pivotal role in fostering communities that can not only endure but also recover from the impacts of disaster events (UNDRR, 2024). The core objective of risk communication is to build a mutual understanding of potential threats among all stakeholders by facilitating collaboration, gathering and sharing relevant information, preparing for emergencies, and managing crises. According to experts, poor or absent communication creates an information void that people are likely to fill with speculation or misinformation (UNDRR, 2024). Therefore, tailoring messages to specific groups is essential—this requires insight into the audience's values and an understanding of why certain messages may be rejected. (PreventionWeb, n.d.)

As defined by the World Health Organization, risk communication involves the timely sharing

of information, guidance, and opinions between experts or officials and individuals who are exposed to dangers that threaten their health, lives, or socioeconomic stability (WHO, 2023). Its purpose is to empower those at risk to make informed choices that reduce harm—such as during disease outbreaks—and to take proactive safety measures. The WHO emphasizes that risk communication is an indispensable element of both emergency readiness and disaster response strategies (WHO, 2023).

Crisis communication and risk communication are the two main ways in which disasters are communicated. The objective to explain an occurrence and its impacts while offering information to lessen harm is widely recognized as one of the primary goals of crisis communication. Risk communication uses persuasive strategies in addition to informational ones to persuade the public to make the right decisions. Due to a lack of information or the propagation of misinformation and rumors, the public may have an inflated view of the hazards connected with a disaster.

Figure 1. Objectives of Risk Communication before, during and after a Hazard Event
Source: Adapted and extended from the Swiss National Platform for Natural Hazards PLANAT, www.planat.ch)

Regardless of the perspective taken—such as the disaster management cycle framework—the goals of risk communication can be distinctly recognized across all phases: prevention, mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery. Figure 1 outlines the specific objectives of risk communication at different stages of a hazardous event: before, during, and after it occurs (Kopper et al., 2012). Broadly

speaking, risk communication serves a set of key purposes: firstly, to deliver information that enables individuals to make well-informed choices to safeguard themselves from danger; secondly, to alleviate fear and anxiety related to potential threats; and thirdly, to establish and strengthen trust among all parties involved in the communication process (Kopper et al., 2012).

Impacts of the Media in Disaster risk communication before, during, and after

As noted by Sharma et al. (2021) and Ranjan (2021), the media holds a pivotal role in disaster management through its capacity to disseminate vital information, offer potential solutions, convey public sentiment, raise awareness, assist in emergency response and relief operations, and contribute to recovery and rehabilitation efforts (Yuliana, 2022; Kapoor, 2015). Often, the media is the initial source through which the public becomes aware of a disaster, effectively setting the tone for how the event is perceived. This initial framing can significantly influence public opinion regarding the handling of the situation and often dictates how much attention and resources are allocated by relevant authorities. Nonetheless, the media also grapples with challenges such as shaping public perception, addressing misinformation, and maintaining objectivity in reporting (Yuliana, 2022; Kapoor, 2015). These complexities explain why the media's influence can be both constructive and detrimental at various stages of a disaster, including during the immediate response and in the aftermath (Dave, n.d.; Kapoor, 2015; Ranjan, 2021; Sharma et al., 2021; Yuliana, 2022).

Positive Contributions of the Media

- According to Nauman (2018), local media outlets are often perceived as reliable sources of timely information, especially within their communities where they have established credibility.
- Continuous, accurate coverage by media networks during and after disasters plays a crucial role in guiding decision-making processes and initiating rapid response actions, which can ultimately help in preserving lives and property.
- In emergency situations, the media serves as a vital communication tool by broadcasting important safety updates, such as road closures, damaged infrastructure, and other public hazards.
- Additionally, the media contributes to addressing broader public health needs by disseminating safety instructions and notifying the public about available medical facilities.

- When traditional communication systems like phones are disrupted, media platforms become essential, both for delivering critical information—such as evacuation instructions—to those affected, and for informing the outside world about the on-the-ground realities of the disaster zone.

- By consistently reporting from the beginning of a crisis, media outlets help raise awareness among both the public and policymakers, guiding appropriate responses even when initial understanding of the risks may be limited.

- Early and ongoing media engagement with at-risk populations enhances the effectiveness of communication efforts throughout the disaster cycle. Moreover, the media acts as a vital link between emergency management authorities and the public, ensuring that essential updates are shared before, during, and after a disaster strikes.

Potential Negative Effects of the Media

- At times, media outlets may amplify certain aspects of a disaster, leading to heightened public anxiety and unnecessary panic.

- Misrepresentations of human behavior in crisis situations are also common, where media may portray events in a sensational or overly dramatic fashion, thereby distorting the reality.

- In certain cases, powerful political figures may exploit media coverage for personal or partisan advantage during times of disaster.

- Sensationalist journalism may result in skewed coverage—for instance, focusing on scenes of severe destruction while ignoring adjacent areas that remain relatively unaffected.

- Such biased reporting can mislead both the public and responders, potentially diverting crucial aid and emergency services away from severely impacted regions to those with lesser need, due to misinformed perceptions.

Community Resilience

Resilience is broadly understood as the capacity of a community, system, or society that is exposed to hazards to effectively withstand, adapt to, and recover from their impacts in a

prompt and organized manner, while maintaining or quickly restoring essential functions and structures (UN, 2007; UNISDR, 2015). According to Adhikari (2020), the level of resilience within a community depends largely on its access to resources and its ability to self-organize before, during, and after a crisis. As such, resilience has become a fundamental concept in the discourse of disaster risk reduction, emergency response, and crisis management.

The United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UNISDR, 2007) defines resilience as the ability to “resist, absorb, accommodate to, and recover from the effects of a hazard in a timely and efficient manner.” This definition serves as a cornerstone for risk management and disaster preparedness strategies, with the primary goal being to reduce the likelihood and impact of hazardous events. Disaster risk management, as outlined by the UNISDR (2011), involves a structured approach that leverages organizational capabilities, administrative systems, and technical skills to implement policies and strengthen response capacity, thereby minimizing the damaging consequences of hazards and reducing disaster risks (Reuter, et al., 2016).

In the context of community-level risk management, it is essential to evaluate both the

vulnerabilities of critical infrastructure and the community’s resilience—its capacity to rebound following a major disruption. Zheng (2011) describes regional and community resilience as the ability to anticipate, prevent, respond to, and recover from both expected and unforeseen threats, such as terrorist attacks or natural disasters. This includes the capacity to adjust to evolving conditions, return to pre-event functioning—or adapt to a new state—and rapidly restore key systems, operations, and services with minimal harm to human health, the economy, environment, and national security.

Additionally, resilience within communities encompasses the capability of a system to absorb shocks, undergo transformation, and yet maintain its core identity, structures, and functions. Longstaff et al. (2010) emphasize that true community resilience lies in the ability to endure disruptions without compromising the foundational attributes of the community itself. According to Datta & Mahjabeen, (2016), early preparedness, disaster response, and resource mobilization will help to build adaptive capacity, while improved adaptive capacity and strength would result in resilient livelihood, social safety, and protection mechanisms, good governance and transformative leadership are key to developing transformative capacity. (See figure 2).

Figure 2. Resilience framework
Source: Datta & Mahjabeen (2016)

Mass Media in Resilience Capacity Building before, during, and after Disaster

The media plays a multifaceted role in society, particularly in the areas of information sharing, public education, and disaster response (Yuliana, 2023). During times of crisis, communication platforms such as radio, mobile phones, television, print media, and social networks become vital tools for delivering timely information and guidance to affected populations. These media outlets serve as essential channels for ensuring that both victims and the broader public stay informed. Clear and efficient communication is not only crucial during the disaster itself but is equally important throughout the recovery phase to support a swift and organized response (Liu et al., 2020; Yandra et al., 2017; Yuliana, 2023).

Disasters fundamentally disrupt the everyday routines and assumptions that define what is considered "normal" in society (Sharma et al., 2021). These events do more than damage physical infrastructure—they can deeply disturb social relationships, cultural expectations, and the overall fabric of community life, challenging long-standing norms and structures. The public's behavior to seek knowledge is compelled to increase as a result of this uncertainty. This heightened awareness and desire for information can lead to more informed decision-making and proactive measures to mitigate risks during and after disasters (Becker et al., 2012). People can take appropriate action to lessen harm when they are informed about the situation's evolving state and the recommended course of action from official sources.

Traditional media is a resource for those in need of emergency information, as well as a way to bring tragedies to the attention of the general public on a national and international level. By reporting on disasters and emergencies, traditional media can raise awareness, mobilize support, and facilitate communication between affected communities and the broader public and authorities (Reilly & Atanasova, 2016). People use the media outlets they are accustomed to and trust during times of crisis. Furthermore, according to DEMA, the public

expects to find reliable information on communication channels with conventional media being one of those. Because traditional media is dependable, steady, and acknowledged as official.

Communities that are disaster-prone or afflicted by disasters could benefit from increased psychological resilience thanks to traditional media. By providing timely and accurate information, traditional media can help reduce anxiety and uncertainty, empower individuals to take action, and foster a sense of community solidarity, all of which contribute to greater psychological resilience in the face of adversity. When a community suffers trauma, the incident results in a shared feeling of shock and loss. When trauma occurs, such as after a disaster, one of the first things individuals do is seek out others to share the experience with.

Social media can be utilized to examine public opinion of disaster response and recovery in addition to serving as a source of information to enhance situational awareness. Analyzing social media activity can provide valuable insights into public perceptions, concerns, and needs during disasters, allowing emergency responders and policymakers to tailor their efforts more effectively and address critical issues in real-time (Smith, 2010). By supplying multimedia content (video, images, and text), users can participate instantly and directly while avoiding professional reporters and journalists and providing unfiltered perspectives on what is happening around the globe. This illustration demonstrates how rapidly people on social media disprove false information and correct inaccurate stories.

Materials & Methods

The Niger Delta region is located in southern Nigeria, encompassing a vast expanse of land between approximately 4°N to 6°N latitude and 5°E to 7°E longitude. This region covers an area of approximately 70,000 square kilometers (27,000 square miles), making it one of the world's largest and most ecologically diverse deltas. Situated at a relatively low elevation, the Niger Delta region is characterized by its proximity to sea level, with an average height

ranging from just a few meters above sea level to slightly higher areas. The delta is a sprawling network of rivers, tributaries, and wetlands, crisscrossed by the Niger and Benue rivers, and eventually emptying into the Gulf of Guinea.

The region is also renowned for its immense oil and gas reserves, making it a vital economic hub for Nigeria and a significant player in the global energy industry.

Figure 3. Three States in the Niger Delta Region showing Spilled Communities

Study Population and Sampling Technique

The study population of respondents was purposively selected from among those residing in nine oil-spill-affected communities across three states in the Niger Delta region and included both males and females that are 18 to 50 years and above. A straightforward random sampling method was employed to choose nine oil spill-affected communities located across Rivers State, Bayelsa State, and Delta State within the Niger Delta region (see Figure 3). To

determine the study's sample size, the Taro Yamane formula was applied, yielding a total of 400 respondents based on the estimated population of 181,406 as outlined in Table 1. In each of the nine communities, a convenient sampling technique was used to collect data. Convenience sampling as the name implies is a specific type of non-probability sampling method in which data are collected within the scope of the study or sampled population who are conveniently available to participate in the study.

Table 1. Names of Nine (9) Impacted Oil-Spilled Communities in Three States of the Niger-Delta Region of Nigeria, Showing their Population and Sampling Size

S/N	Name of communities	Population of Communities in 1991	Projected Population of 2022	Sampled %
1	Agoro community	2,311	13,001	40
2	Okokokiri community	742	4,174	26

3	Otein Biseni community	705	3,966	25
4	Amuokpokpor- Elume community	1,401	7,882	30
5	Mereje community	2,813	15,825	40
6	Polobubo Tsekelewu community	1,668	9,384	37
7	Bodo community	9,387	52,811	67
8	Odua community	1,589	8,939	35
9	Onne communit	11,629	65,424	100
Total		32,245	181,406	400

Source: National Population Commission Office in Rivers State, Bayelsa State and Delta State (Projected population of 1991 to 2022).

Results and Discussion

Contribution of the mass media in resilience capacity building before, during, and after a disaster in the Niger Delta

Table 2 shows the result of the contribution of various mass media in resilience capacity building before, during, and after a disaster in the Niger Delta. Item 1 shows that 36.5% strongly agreed, 30.9% agreed, 46% 16.3% disagreed and 11.7% strongly disagreed that the mass media in the Niger Delta adequately represents the concerns and interests of oil-spilled

communities. Therefore, the majority of the respondents revealed that 36.5% strongly agreed. 28.6% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that they trust the information provided by the mass media regarding environmental issues in the Niger Delta, 32.1% agreed, 10.5% undecided, 13.8% disagreed, and 15.1% strongly disagreed. 30.1% strongly agreed, 36.7% agreed, 6.1% undecided, 14.3% disagreed and 12.8% strongly disagreed that mass media plays a significant role in holding government and oil companies accountable for the consequences of oil-spills in the Niger Delta.

Table 2. Contribution of Various Mass media in Resilience Capacity Building before, during, and after a disaster (n=392)

S/N	Item	Responses	Respondents	Percentage
1.	The mass media in the Niger Delta adequately represents the concerns and interests of oil-spilled communities	(a) SA	143	36.5
		(b) A	121	30.9
		(c) Undecided	18	4.6
		(d) D	64	16.3
		(e) SD	46	11.7
		Total	392	100
2.	I trust the information provided by themass media regardingenvironmental issues in the Niger Delta	(a) SA	112	28.6
		(b) A	126	32.1
		(c) Undecided	41	10.5
		(d) D	54	13.8
		(e) SD	59	14.9
		Total	392	100
3.	The mass media platforms effectively communicate the environmental risks and hazards associated with oil spills in the Niger Delta	(a) SA	118	30.1
		(b) A	144	36.8
		(c) Undecided	24	6.1
		(d) D	56	14.3
		(e) SD	50	12.8
		Total	392	100
114.	I trust the mass media to provide accurate and unbiased information about the causes and consequences of oil spills	(a) SA	137	34.9
		(b) A	128	32.7
		(c) Undecided	23	5.9
		(d) D	54	13.8
		(e) SD	50	12.8
		Total	392	100

5.	Mass media campaigns have played a significant role in shaping public opinion and policy responses towards oil spills in the Niger Delta	(a) SA	108	27.6
		(b) A	152	38.8
		(c) Undecided	34	8.7
		(d) D	55	14.0
		(e) SD	43	11.0
		Total	392	100

Further, 34.9% of these respondents strongly agreed with the statement that they feel that mass media adequately informs them about the available resources and support system for affected communities in the Niger Delta, 32.7% agreed, 5.9% were undecided, while 3.8% disagreed and 12.8% strongly disagreed. Therefore, most of the respondents in item 16 representing 34.9% strongly agreed. Finally, the

result of item 17 shows that 27.6% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that mass media platforms effectively communicate the environmental risks and hazards associated with oil spills in Niger, 38.8% agreed, 38.7% were undecided, 14.0% disagreed and 11.0% strongly disagreed. Therefore, the majority of the respondents in item 17 representing 38.8% agreed.

Table 3. Summary of Model Table on Multiple Regression Analysis on the Contribution of Various Mass Media in Resilience Capacity Building before, during, and after a disaster in the Niger Delta (n=392)

Variables	\bar{X}	S	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate	Sig
**I trust the information provided by the mass media	2.3597	±1.41266	.071	.005	-.008	2.76976	.853
**Mass media adequately represent the viewpoint of the community	2.5459	±1.41527					
**Mass media plays a significant	2.4286	±1.37942					
**Mass media inform me about the available support system	2.3673	±1.40614					
**Mass media communicate the environmental risk hazard	2.4209	±1.40614					
*Communities	4.9031	±2.75900					

Key: * Dependent variable; **Predictors(constant).

Table 3 shows the summary of the model table of Multiple Regression Analysis on the contribution of various mass media in resilience capacity building before, during, and after a disaster in the Niger Delta. R=.071 which is the

multiple correlation coefficient among the variables. Rsquare=.005 which shows the proportion of the dependent variable that has been accounted for by the independent variables.

Table 4. ANOVA Summary Table for Multiple Regression Analysis on Multiple Regression Analysis on the Contribution of Various Mass Media in Resilience Capacity Building before, during, and after a disaster in Niger Delta (n=392)

Source of Variance	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	P-Value
Regression	5	15.087	3.017	.393	0.853
Residual	386	2961.229	7.672		
Total	391	2976.316			Significant predictors

Table 4 shows the ANOVA summary for multiple regression analysis on the contribution of various mass media in resilience capacity building before, during, and after a disaster in the Niger Delta. The results showed that the five independent variables that I trust the information provided by the mass media, Mass media adequately represents the viewpoint of the community, Mass media plays a significant, Mass media informs me about available support systems, and Mass media communicates the environmental risk hazard) are significant predictors of mass media effectiveness of communication strategies in oil-spilled communities in the Niger Delta, ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

The main purpose of this paper was to examine the contribution of various mass media in resilience capacity building before, during, and after a disaster in Niger Delta. While acknowledging the strengths of the media in disaster management including its ability to provide real-time coverage of rescue and relief efforts, create public awareness, disseminate useful information and alerts, connect citizens for support, and coordinate volunteer actions, it sees the social media emerging as a powerful tool in disaster management, but its use varies among different communities and is influenced by factors such as vulnerability, personal effort, and task complexity.

According to the findings, it was revealed that mass media platforms effectively communicate the environmental risk and hazards associated with oil spills in the Niger Delta (38.8%) agreed. It was also, indicated in the findings that (28.6%) of the sample respondents claimed that they the information provided by the mass media regarding environmental issues in the Niger Delta, while 32.7% of the sample respondents agreed that they feel that mass media adequately inform them about the available resources and support system for affected communities in the Niger Delta.

Based on these findings, the following recommendations were made: There should be increased sensitization by the government

through seminars and workshops on mass media usage, and community participation on there silence capacity building of oil spilled communities in the Niger Delta, should embark on the awareness campaign on the mass media usage that will improve the knowledge and attitude of the community on the resilience capacity building of oil spilled communities in the Niger Delta. In line with *NOSDRA (2023) mandate*, other appropriate government agencies should carry out more awareness campaigns through mass media on community participation in how to build and strengthen the resilience capacity of oil-spilled communities in the Niger Delta.

Ultimately, it has become increasingly vital that risk communication be recognized as an essential element within the disaster risk management framework (UNDRR, 2023). This calls for robust capacity development across various sectors—including the media, disaster response agencies, scientific communities, stakeholders, local leaders, and academic institutions. Strengthening expertise in areas such as disaster risk reduction, effective communication strategies, media literacy, and the ability of scientists to convey complex information to non-specialist audiences is fundamental. Such efforts are crucial to bolstering the resilience of vulnerable communities, particularly those affected by recurring oil spills in the oil-producing regions of the Niger Delta. As emphasized by UNDRR (2023), "effective risk communication saves lives and strengthens disaster resilience."

To enhance the media's role in disaster scenarios—before, during, and after—strong, direct collaboration between media organizations, disaster response bodies, and relevant stakeholders must be initiated, nurtured, and continually reinforced (Sarma, 2021). Historical evidence suggests that consistent engagement with media outlets ahead of disasters significantly facilitates information flow and lays a solid foundation for post-disaster cooperation. Therefore, such practices should become standard, alongside efforts to enhance the communication capacity of media

professionals themselves. Furthermore, in today's digital era, leveraging modern communication technologies is imperative for the timely dissemination of critical information and should be actively promoted and optimized.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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